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Global ICT Access

It increased by an average of 61.29% between 2013 and 2022 for the countries considered.

Access to Information and Communication Technologies (ICT Access) is an indicator that measures the availability and use of digital technologies essential for communication, information, and innovation. This variable takes into account several factors, including internet access, the spread of mobile devices, the penetration of fixed and mobile lines, the availability of computers and other digital devices, as well as economic accessibility and the quality of network infrastructure. ICT Access is considered a crucial element in evaluating a country's technological and digital development, as it forms the foundation for adopting advanced technologies, digital inclusion, and economic and social participation. A high level of ICT access is often associated with a robust digital ecosystem, where citizens and businesses can easily access online services, participate in global networks of knowledge and innovation, and leverage the opportunities offered by digitalization in sectors such as education, healthcare, and the economy. On the other hand, limited ICT access reflects the presence of economic, infrastructural, and social barriers that hinder full participation in the digital society. This gap, known as the digital divide, can have significant impacts on economic growth, social inclusion, and access to global opportunities. Measuring and improving ICT access is therefore a key objective for governments and international organizations to promote inclusive and sustainable development.

Access to ICT in 2022. Access to information and communication technologies (ICT) is a crucial element for the economic, social, and cultural development of a country. The analysis of 2022 data reveals a significant disparity between nations in terms of ICT access, reflecting deep differences in economic development, infrastructure, investments, and government policies. At the top of the ranking, we find Singapore, with ICT access at 99.6%, followed by the United Arab Emirates and Hong Kong at 98.2%. These countries have heavily invested in digital infrastructure, developing highly advanced technological ecosystems and offering citizens near-universal access to the internet, digital devices, and online services. Their strategic geographic position as financial and commercial hubs has further incentivized the development of advanced ICT networks, making these nations global leaders in technological adoption. Other European countries such as Cyprus, Luxembourg, and Iceland follow with percentages above 97%, demonstrating how a stable political environment, long-term investments, and a relatively small population can facilitate widespread access to digital technologies. In general, European nations dominate the top positions in the ranking, reflecting the European Union's strong commitment to promoting digital inclusion and reducing the digital divide across different regions. Middle Eastern countries like Saudi Arabia, Kuwait, and Qatar also show high levels of ICT access, thanks to government policies aimed at diversifying the economy and reducing reliance on oil, with a growing focus on digitalization and technological innovation. East Asia includes nations like South Korea and Japan, known for their high-quality digital infrastructure developed through decades of public and private investment. South Korea, in particular, is renowned for having one of the fastest and most widespread internet connections in the world, with ICT access at 95%, a result of educational policies that promote digital literacy from primary schools and a dynamic and ever-expanding technological ecosystem. Moving towards Eastern Europe and Central Asia, countries like Armenia, Georgia, and Kazakhstan show access rates between 90% and 93%, demonstrating the progress made in regions that, until a few decades ago, were significantly behind

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in terms of digitalization. In these cases, international collaboration, often with the support of organizations like the World Bank, has played a crucial role in modernizing ICT infrastructure and improving public access to the internet and digital technologies. However, despite these successes, significant disparities still exist within the same regions. In Southern Europe, for instance, countries like Italy, with ICT access at 88.1%, lag slightly behind the European average. This result can be attributed to a combination of factors, including complex bureaucracy, inconsistent infrastructure investments, and an uneven distribution of internet connections across the country, with the south suffering more from a lack of high-speed connections. A similar situation is observed in Latin American countries such as Brazil (81.4%) and Mexico (77.2%), where, despite rapid digital infrastructure development, there remain significant challenges related to accessibility in rural and less developed areas. South Asia and Southeast Asia present a wide heterogeneity: nations like Vietnam (90.5%) have made significant progress in digitalization, while others like India (70.4%) show a stark digital divide between different regions of the country, with a large portion of the rural population still excluded from basic ICT services. African countries like Morocco (90.7%) represent positive examples of how strategic resource management and targeted policies can lead to a significant increase in ICT access, but across much of the continent, access levels remain low. Nations like Ghana (72.4%), Nigeria (56.6%), and Ethiopia (36.8%) face enormous infrastructural and socioeconomic challenges that limit the expansion of ICT networks, leaving large sections of the population without connection or with limited and poor-quality access. In these contexts, a lack of investment, political instability, and economic difficulties represent significant obstacles to digital progress. The extreme case is represented by Myanmar, with virtually non-existent ICT access in 2022, a sign of a country that has undergone severe political and military crises that have paralyzed any attempt at technological development. Overall, the data reflect a highly heterogeneous global landscape where countries with more developed and stable economies tend to dominate the higher positions, while those developing or plagued by political instability lag behind. This inequality in ICT access not only highlights economic disparities but also has profound social, educational, and labor implications. In an increasingly interconnected world, access to digital technologies is a key element for economic growth, democratic participation, and poverty reduction. Therefore, for countries at the lower end of the ranking, it will be crucial to adopt inclusive development policies aimed at overcoming infrastructural and economic barriers, with a greater focus on investments in digital technologies and training the skills necessary to fully participate in the global digital economy.

Access to ICT between 2013 and 2022. The analysis of ICT access data between 2013 and 2022 highlights diverse trends based on socioeconomic contexts and the priorities of different countries. During the period considered, some countries recorded significant improvements, often linked to targeted investments and policies promoting the expansion of digital infrastructure and technological inclusion. Bangladesh, for example, saw a 297.91% increase, raising its ICT access level from 19.1% in 2013 to 76% in 2022. This result can be attributed to the adoption of government policies favorable to digitalization and the widespread distribution of mobile networks, which have extended access to a wide portion of the population, including rural areas. Similarly, the Kyrgyz Republic, with a growth of 254.2%, has significantly expanded its connectivity, benefiting from initiatives aimed at modernizing digital infrastructure and improving internet access in remote regions. Sub-Saharan Africa also shows notable progress, with countries like Zambia (+290.23%), Ghana (+244.76%), and Kenya (+221.79%) registering significant increases. In these countries, the growing spread of mobile networks and the adoption of innovative low-cost access solutions, such as mobile digital payments, have greatly contributed to the expansion of ICT access. However, despite these increases, many of these countries start from a very low initial level, indicating that while progress has been made, the gap with more developed countries remains substantial. The expansion of digital networks in Africa and Asia, while significant, underscores the need for further investments to ensure adequate connection quality and more equitable access distribution between urban and rural areas. On the other hand, some high-income developed countries, such as Sweden (+10.12%), Iceland (+10.1%), and

Switzerland (+4.84%), have shown modest improvements, reflecting a saturation of ICT access, which is already near 100% for most of the population. This scenario suggests that in highly developed contexts, efforts are now focused more on the quality of infrastructure and the integration of emerging technologies rather than on expanding basic connectivity. In contrast, countries like Hong Kong and Singapore, which already had high levels of ICT access in 2013, still recorded significant improvements of 6.62% and 18.85%, respectively, reaching nearly total population coverage. These increases indicate not only better penetration but also a transition to more advanced services and higher-quality connectivity, including 5G infrastructure and next-generation cloud services. Looking at Latin America, countries like Colombia (+104.56%) and Peru (+81.91%) have made notable progress in expanding ICT access, with growth driven by digital inclusion policies, government support programs, and the expansion of mobile networks. However, the digital divide within these nations remains significant, with rural areas still lagging behind major urban centers. Nations like China (+113.83%) and India (+183.87%) also stand out for their significant increase in ICT access, although the size and geographic diversity of these countries present considerable challenges in ensuring equitable distribution of access. In China, connectivity expansion has benefited from massive investments in digital infrastructure, with the government actively promoting digital inclusion as part of its national development strategy. In India, the rise in ICT access is mainly linked to the exponential growth in smartphone usage and the spread of low-cost data plans, which have made internet access possible for millions of people. On the other hand, it is interesting to note that while many emerging countries have shown significant percentage growth, developed countries have recorded smaller but still substantial absolute increases. The United States, with a 19.33% increase, and the United Kingdom, with 13.22%, are examples of nations where market saturation has not prevented further improvements, particularly through the expansion of next-generation networks and the integration of ICT into everyday economic activities. European countries like France (+11.99%) and Germany (+5.77%) show more moderate growth rates, reflecting a greater focus on access quality and reducing digital disparities between different regions. However, even in these advanced contexts, significant differences persist between urban and rural areas, requiring targeted interventions to close the digital divide. In conclusion, the data presented highlights how the period from 2013 to 2022 was characterized by a significant expansion in ICT access, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, where digital inclusion has been driven by technological innovations and proactive government policies. However, progress remains uneven, with countries like Bangladesh, Kenya, and Uzbekistan making significant strides, while others, despite improving, show more limited growth due to economic, infrastructural, and social factors. In developed countries, percentage growth has been less impressive, but high penetration rates and a focus on service quality indicate a transition to a more mature phase of digitalization. The global challenge for the next decade will therefore be not only to further expand ICT access but to ensure that it is equitably distributed, of high quality, and capable of supporting the adoption of emerging technologies in an inclusive and sustainable manner.

Economic policies for ICT Access. The development of access to information and communication technologies (ICT Access) requires a set of integrated economic policies aimed at improving digital infrastructure, increasing connectivity, and reducing the digital divide between different geographic areas and social groups. A crucial first step is investing in network infrastructure, such as broadband and next-generation mobile networks (4G, 5G). Governments can incentivize private investments in these infrastructures through tax breaks, grants, and public-private partnerships, while ensuring a regulatory framework that promotes competition and lowers costs for end users. It is essential to ensure that rural and remote areas, often neglected by private operators due to low profitability, are covered by connectivity programs subsidized or incentivized by the state. Another key strategy is expanding access to digital devices, such as smartphones, tablets, and computers, through subsidy policies, loan programs, or technology recycling initiatives. This can include programs that offer discounted devices to low-income families or educational institutions. Alongside these measures, it is crucial to promote digital literacy, ensuring that the population has the skills needed to effectively

use ICT technologies. Investing in digital training and reskilling programs, both through the formal education system and lifelong learning initiatives, is essential to create a workforce capable of fully leveraging the opportunities offered by digitalization. Governments can also adopt policies to encourage the adoption of ICT in the public sector, making essential services such as healthcare, education, and administration accessible online. This not only stimulates demand for digital services but also creates a favorable environment for the development of technological innovation and e-government. Finally, promoting a regulatory framework that protects privacy and digital security is crucial to strengthen trust in ICT and encourage widespread and informed use of technologies. Through a coordinated set of these policies, a country can develop an inclusive and sustainable ICT ecosystem, reducing the digital divide and fostering balanced and innovative economic growth.

Conclusions. The value of ICT access grew by an average of 61.29% between 2013 and 2022 for the countries considered. There are countries where the value of ICT access increased significantly, such as Bangladesh with +297.91%, Zambia with +290.23%, Kyrgyz Republic with +254.20%, Ghana with +244.76%, and Nepal with +236.9%. On the other hand, there are countries where ICT access grew less than the period average, such as Sweden with +10.12%, Iceland with +10.1%, Hong Kong with +6.62%, Germany with +5.77%, and Switzerland with +4.84%.

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